

Human Meaning of Primary Education in Shaanxi- Gansu-Ningxia Border Region during the Total Anti-Japanese War

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Abstract: *Comprehensive anti-Japanese period, under the leadership of the communist party of China and it's the shensi-kansu-ningxia border region despite facing huge pressure of the war, for primary school education serves the needs of the Anti-Japanese War, but in the process of development of primary school education does not ignore the human thought by Marx and Engels, but under the guidance of Marx and Engels human thought, the pursuit of the all-round development of children's body and mind, Combining primary school education with social practice, paying attention to the essence of social practice of primary school students, and clarifying the value orientation of primary school students becoming soldiers of the anti-Japanese war and founding the country, citizens of new democracy and building new democracy, thus promoting the development and progress of primary school education in Shaanxi-Gansu-Ningxia Border Region.*

Keywords: *Total War of Resistance against Japanese Aggression, Shaanxi-Gansu-Ningxia Border Region, Primary Education, Humanities*

After the outbreak of the comprehensive anti-Japanese war of resistance, in order to accumulate the strength, change the Shaanxi-Gansu-Ningxia border area (hereinafter referred to as the "border area") backward social appearance, the Communist Party of China in the border area not only led the social development and progress of the new democracy construction, and including education in the border area all construction undertakings must serve the needs of the war of resistance. However, in spite of this, the Communist Party of China, as a Marxist political party, has always adhered to the basic principles and theoretical direction of Marxism, in the education cause, especially in primary school education in accordance with the basic requirements of Marx and Engels' learning thought to train primary school students, so that the primary school education in the border region on the correct development direction.

I. THE PURSUIT OF ALL-ROUND DEVELOPMENT: THE DEVELOPMENT OF CHILDREN'S BODY AND MIND

It is the ultimate goal of Marx and Engels to strive for the freedom and liberation of all mankind and to realize the comprehensive and free development of everyone. Marx and Engels pointed out in "The Communist Manifesto" that, because of the popularization of machine production and the in-depth development of the division of labor, the independence of workers' labor has been lost, and workers themselves have become appendages of the machine. At the same time, he points out that in bourgeois society, only capital, as a social force, "has independence and individuality, while the active individual does not". Therefore, it is impossible for workers, who are tightly bound by machines and capital, to achieve comprehensive and free development in the bourgeois society. For this reason, Marx and Engels believed that if workers wanted to change their own destiny and realize their own comprehensive and free development, they must overthrow and transform the bourgeois society in an all-round way, and make themselves the material and spiritual wealth of the society and their own masters. Marx and Engels in the communist manifesto stresses in the proletariat to overthrow of bourgeois society, create advanced proletarian society, not only to win all of their capital, change all the capitalist mode of production, finance and economic reform, but also to "implements public and free education for all children", "combination of education with industrial production" [1]. Obviously, Marx and Engels attached great importance to children's education, thought that in the proletarian society, the development of education, everyone to receive education is to change everyone's destiny, to achieve everyone's comprehensive and free development of an important path and necessary conditions.

Comprehensive Anti-Japanese War broke out, the Japanese invaders crazy attack and under the condition of continuous fall in north China, the CPC Central Committee and the border region face enormous pressure of the war, to mobilize all the forces can be mobilized to ensure victory in the war of resistance, thus put forward all the culture education career must serve the needs of the war of resistance against Japan, and clearly the aim of education is "to strive for the victory of the war of resistance against Japan, To build an independent, free and happy New China, and to train soldiers and builders who have national consciousness, democratic style, knowledge and skills of modern life, and can shoulder the task of the Anti-Japanese War and the founding of the country ". However, the party central committee and the border region have not therefore ignore the all-round development of primary school students, but actively practicing the human thought and the education view of Marx and Engels, on the one hand, the education of universal free education policy, for 7 years old of above of school-age children and adults who drop out of school to popularize the minimum free education, in order to make ", regardless of gender composition and age are the equal opportunity of education, Liberate the broad masses from illiteracy "; On the other hand, legislation on primary education is carried out, which clearly stipulates that children's physical and mental development and all-round development should be promoted in the form of law. For example, the Primary Schools Law of Shaanxi-Gan-Ningxia Border Region enacted in August 1938 stipulates that primary schools in the border areas must "develop children's physical and mental health, cultivate their

national consciousness, revolutionary spirit and basic knowledge and skills necessary for the Anti-Japanese War and the founding of the country". In February 1941 the implementation summary of the shensi-kansu-ningsia border region elementary education requires the border region primary school education must be in accordance with the new democratic education policy "to promote the national consciousness of children, foster children's democratic style of work, inspire children's scientific thinking, develop children's aesthetic idea, improving the labor interest of children, exercise the robust physique of children, promote children's life the necessary knowledge, Cultivate children's spirit of serving the public ". The principles and policies of the Party Central Committee and the Border Region on primary education do not stay in the theoretical level, but set up a more comprehensive learning curriculum in the concrete teaching practice to implement these principles and policies. Whether it includes a grade, grade two and grade three of primary school, still include the 4th and 5th grade senior primary school, have set up mandarin lessons, math class, include politics, nature, history, geography, common knowledge, as well as the art class, working class, music class, P.E. class, these courses reflects the political, the characteristics of the knowledge, practical, Can make the pupil learns the various cultural knowledge, and obtains the physical exercise and the heart temper in the study. At the same time, the border area stipulates that all primary schools shall not corporal punishment students, provide students with a variety of reading materials, and "strive to fit the physical and mental development of children, pay attention to the connection between collective learning and individual learning, so as to inspire their automaticity, creativity and independence" [2]. All these can promote the all-round development of primary school students in the border area.

II. PAY ATTENTION TO THE NATURE OF HUMAN SOCIAL PRACTICE: THE COMBINATION OF PRIMARY EDUCATION AND SOCIAL PRACTICE

Human beings have both natural and social attributes. According to Marx and Engels, the essence of human beings lies in their social attributes. However, as a "realistic person", his social attribute is not abstract existence, but gradually formed in the participation of various social practice activities. Marx attaches great importance to practice. He believes that everything of human beings comes from social and creative practice, including the whole social life, various social relations and ideological consciousness of human beings, as well as the changes of environment and human beings themselves. The ideology of human beings not only comes from social practice, but also measures the objectivity and truth of its content by practice. At the same time, Marx deeply realized that people's ideology is "with the change of people's living conditions, people's social relations, people's social existence. It is actually pointed out that people's ideology is changed with the change of social practice. Engels also attached great importance to practice. He believed that labor practice played a crucial role in the reason that human beings had social attributes and could be distinguished from other animals in nature. Because of Marx and Engels deeply realize the social practice to change people's social life, social relations and ideology has a pivotal role, so in the "communist manifesto" to the "combination of education with industrial

production" [3], to strengthen the contact with the social practice of interaction and educatees, better play to the education of the positive role to promote the development of social production.

In the period of democratic revolution, it can be said that the combination of education and social practice is not only the inevitable choice for the Communist Party of China to win the revolutionary struggle, but also the concrete manifestation of the practice of Marx and Engels' humanistic thought and the emphasis on the essence of human social practice. As early as during the agrarian revolution, the Communist Party of China in the Central Soviet Area proposed to closely link educational activities with productive labor. After the outbreak of the all-out war of resistance against Japanese aggression, under the situation that the Japanese aggressors were constantly approaching the border regions and sending traitors and spies to undermine social stability and development in the border regions, the border regions strengthened anti-Japanese war and labor education among students. In March 1938, the Education Department of the Border Region required primary school students to learn detective work, news transmission, comfort work and other labor work. At the same time, they used their morning and evening breaks to report the war situation to the peasants and teach them to read and write. In December, in the border region department of education to clarify the national defense education guidelines emphasize education should not only become one and social life, "according to the study and real life closely linked", and should, "with a special focus on labor education", the young children to exercise the body, "the development of their collective spirit", develop "labor interests and value of labor habit". In order to implement the primary school education and social practice of combining the education idea, no.12, border region in 1939 work plan, must strengthen student's productive labor, every primary school to farm, engage in food production, and according to their own specific conditions to develop handicraft industry and animal husbandry production, and set up the working class, with specific labor education. Under the promotion of the Department of Education in the Border Region, all the regions in the Border Region combined education with social practice in the process of developing primary education. For example, in April 1943, Wubao County decided to take production practice as the teaching content and "supplement practical knowledge about production, combine extracurricular activities with book knowledge, instruct students to attach importance to labor and help family production". Chunyao County in the primary school education in the combination of after-school production and learning, specifically, some primary school students are divided into dung collection group and textile group, respectively engaged in carrying dung and spinning labor; Some primary schools organize students to help farmers cut grain and corn during the busy farming season. Suide District earnestly implements the educational policy of combining school with social practice, requiring all students over the age of 12 to participate in productive labor. Boys are engaged in twirling wool, planting vegetables and cutting firewood, and girls are engaged in sewing. At the same time, the little teacher system is implemented, and primary school students are encouraged to participate in literacy classes, half-day classes, public blackboard teaching and publicity activities, so as to teach literacy for the doll changers [4]. The combination of school education and social practice in the border area can not only effectively promote the overall development of primary school students, but also strengthen the inner connection between primary school students and the society and shape their social practice ability to adapt to the needs of The Times.

III. CLARIFYING THE VALUE OF HUMAN EXISTENCE: TO BE A SOLDIER OF THE ANTI-JAPANESE WAR AND THE FOUNDING OF THE COUNTRY, A CITIZEN OF THE NEW DEMOCRACY AND THE CONSTRUCTION OF THE NEW DEMOCRACY

As a "realistic person", it is not a value-free pursuit, but a personal value pursuit to achieve personal goals and gain personal interests, as well as a social value pursuit to achieve the development and progress of the society, the nation, the country and even the whole mankind. Therefore, people have "existence value". At the same time, generally speaking, the individual value appeal of a person is not only beneficial to the individual and satisfies his personal interests, but also beneficial to the society, the nation, the country and even the whole mankind. Therefore, the realization of the individual value appeal of a person often means that the social value appeal has been realized to a considerable extent. However, when the society, the nation, the country and even the whole mankind are faced with many sufferings and disasters and are in urgent need of people with lofty ideals to change them, the value of human existence should be mainly reflected in the aspect of social value, that is, the value appeal of human should be mainly social value appeal. As a great proletarian revolutionist and thinkers, Marx and Engels in the face of Europe and the United States of the proletariat is the bourgeoisie cruel oppression and exploitation that case, the commitment to the overall liberation struggle of the proletariat, as early as the youth which Marx set up to fight for human happiness life goal in life. Therefore, Marx and Engels argued that the value of human existence mainly lies in its social value, and the demand of social value should be higher than that of individual value.

During the period of the total war of resistance against Japanese aggression, the Party Central Committee and the border areas did not neglect the teaching and clarification of the value of human existence, that is, individual value and social value. In the case of economic backwardness and material shortage in the border area, people in the border area are undoubtedly more interested in how to improve their material life and better carry out material production practice. In response, the Department of Education of the Border Region not only stipulated that primary schools should combine productive labor, physical exercise and teaching activities, carry out labor and physical education classes and organize students to participate in various production practices, but also urged primary schools to transform the curriculum content. Increased the abacus progressive tax, government policy, law, agriculture, peasants and business health and other practical common sense, common sense and science closely related to the life, so that students master the written contract and communication, receipt and the ability to report, the article open and basic production and living knowledge, can effectively help improve material production and living at home. Such as yan 'an complete primary school in 1943, a new teaching approach, in addition to the opening, in accordance with the relevant regulations of un-con, increased to more than four grade students' attributes, write, write, flagging, written contract, the abacus ", such as teaching content, changing the pupils in the school learn can't serve the masses ", It also strongly promoted the people to "improve their lives day by day" and "automatically send their children to school". However, at that time, on the one hand, the party central

committee should lead the people in the border area to carry out the arduous war of resistance against Japanese aggression; on the other hand, it should lead the people in the border area to carry out the construction of new democracy in politics, economy, culture and other aspects, and devote itself to building the border area into a model area for new democracy. Therefore, the CPC Central Committee and the border region hope to train children and teenagers in the border region to become soldiers of the anti-Japanese war and new democratic citizens and to be able to support the anti-Japanese war and build new democratic China through the development of primary education. In 1940, the border region began to implement a three-year plan for universal education, which clearly stipulated that more than 80,000 children in the border region were not only new soldiers of the Anti-Japanese War and the founding of the country, but also masters of the new China, and builders of the new Chinese society. Schools such as Suide District Full Primary School clearly require pupils to study hard, speed up production, help their families and serve the society, and strive to be a good student of the school, a good child of the family and a good citizen of the society [5]. In November 1944, the Culture and Education Conference of the Border Region clearly stipulated in the draft resolution on the education policy of the Border Region that the goal of primary education in the Border Region was to cultivate new democratic citizens who could know more than 500 words, master addition, subtraction, multiplication and division, have preliminary political and health knowledge, and have the habit of productive labor [6]. In fact, all these show that the CPC Central Committee and the Border Region have made clear the existence value of primary school students as "realistic people", that is, they hope that primary school students can become the soldiers of the Anti-Japanese War and the founding of the country and the citizens of the New Democracy, and then strive to build the New Democracy and New China.

In short, after the outbreak of the all-out war of resistance against Japanese aggression, the frantic invasion of the Japanese invaders was the biggest threat to the Communist Party of China and the border region at that time, and the defeat of the Japanese invaders was the top priority for the Communist Party of China and the border region at that time. Therefore, all construction undertakings and all work in the border areas, including primary school education, must serve the needs of the war of resistance. However, as a Marxist political party, the Communist Party of China did not ignore Marx and Engels' thoughts on human studies because of the cruel war environment. Border areas under its direct leadership actively practiced Marx and Engels' thoughts on human studies in the process of developing primary school education, not only pursuing the all-round development of primary school students, but also pursuing the comprehensive development of primary school students. Moreover, it pays attention to the essence of social practice of primary school students and makes clear the value orientation of primary school students, which will definitely promote the development and progress of primary school education in border area.

REFERENCES

- [1] Selected Works of Marx and Engels (Vol.1),in Central Compilation & Translation Bureau (Ed.), (Beijing: People's Publishing House, 2012):407-422.

- [2] Educational materials of Shaanxi Gansu Ningxia border region (primary education: Part I),in institute of education of Shaanxi Normal University (Ed.),(Beijing: Educational Science Press, 1981):26-61.
- [3] Selected Works of Marx and Engels (Vol. 1),in Central Compilation & Translation Bureau (Ed.),(Beijing: People's Publishing House, 2012):134-422.
- [4] Educational materials of Shaanxi Gansu Ningxia border region (primary education: Part I),in institute of education of Shaanxi Normal University (Ed.),(Beijing: Educational Science Press, 1981):2-138.
- [5] Educational materials of Shaanxi Gansu Ningxia border region (primary education: Part I),in institute of education of Shaanxi Normal University (Ed.),(Beijing: Educational Science Press, 1981):70-285.
- [6] Educational materials of Shaanxi Gansu Ningxia border region (Education policy: Part II),in institute of education of Shaanxi Normal University (Ed.),(Beijing: Educational Science Press, 1981):443.